

ISSN: 2814-063X

BASUG LAW JOURNAL

**VOLUME 3
ISSUE 1
2025**

BASUG

LAW JOURNAL

Volume 3, Issue 1, 2025

**Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University
2025**

BASUG Law Journal Volume 3 Issue 1 2025

Published by:

Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University (formerly Bauchi State University)
For more information, see: **www.basuglawjournal.com**

To order:

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Sa'adu Zungur University, Gadau
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ISSN: 2814-063X

THIS JOURNAL SHOULD BE CITED AS BASUGLJ Volume 3 No 1 2025

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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

**LOCUS STANDI IN NIGERIAN ENVIRONMENTAL
LITIGATION: A REVIEW OF *CENTRE FOR OIL POLLUTION
WATCH V NNPC***

By

Abubakar Garba,* Goni Usman, Ahmed Mohammed Abdulkadir*****
Abstract

*Environmental degradation has continued to affect communities through activities such as oil spills, gas flaring, industrial pollution, mining and other harmful environmental practices. Yet, many victims have been unable to access justice due to numerous challenges within the legal system. A major obstacle has been the restrictive application of the doctrine of locus standi which led to the failure of several environmental claims. Non-governmental organisations, affected individuals and concerned citizens have been barred from initiating actions aimed at protecting environmental rights, public health and human life. This has rendered the legal system seemingly unjust, inefficient and inaccessible in environmental matters. However, in a landmark judgment, the Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch V NNPC*¹ liberalised the traditional approach to locus standi thereby allowing NGOs to litigate on behalf of victims of environmental degradation. This paper examines how the common law rules on locus standi have historically impeded environmental justice, and how the recent decision signals a doctrinal shift. Adopting a doctrinal research method, the paper further recommends legislative reform to fully align the law on standing with international best practices.*

Keywords: *Locus standi, Environmental Justice, Access to justice, public interest litigation*

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¹ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt.1666) 518 SC

1.0 Introduction

Around the world, the protection of the environment is not merely a legal issue but a question of human survival, public health, and intergenerational equity.² Yet, despite its importance, environmental law has often struggled with procedural barriers that prevent those most affected from obtaining justice. One of the most significant of these barriers is the doctrine of *locus standi*, the legal capacity to bring a matter before the court. In many jurisdictions, this doctrine has been applied narrowly, requiring litigants to demonstrate a direct and personal interest in the matter before the court will hear their case. This restrictive approach has, in practice, meant that numerous instances of environmental harm go unchallenged, not because the harm is in doubt, but because those willing to act on behalf of the environment are told they lack the legal standing to do so.

Nigeria is no exception to this challenge. Over the years, its courts have consistently insisted that a person seeking to sue must show that their civil rights or obligations have been infringed or are in imminent danger, and that they have a sufficient legal interest in the matter. While this requirement might make sense in conventional civil disputes, it has proved to be a formidable obstacle in environmental cases, where the harm is often diffused, affects communities rather than individuals, and may take years to manifest fully. As a result, affected communities, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and concerned citizens have often found themselves shut out of the judicial process, even in cases where environmental degradation is severe and ongoing.

The consequence has been a troubling gap between environmental harm and environmental accountability. Oil spills, gas flaring, industrial discharges, and mining pollution continue to scar Nigeria's ecosystems, jeopardising livelihoods, health, and biodiversity. Yet victims are frequently left without an effective remedy, and NGOs seeking to act in the public interest have been barred from pursuing claims. The rigidity of *locus standi* rules has therefore not only stifled environmental justice but

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² Pathak P, Human Rights Approach to Environmental Protection, available at <http://www.ssrn.com/link/OIDA-Intl-journal-sustainable-dev.html>. accessed on 12 February 2025

has also undermined public confidence in the legal system's ability to protect collective rights and the environment.

Against this backdrop, the Supreme Court's [2019](#) decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation* marked a significant turning point. In a progressive departure from the narrow common law tradition, the Court recognised the right of an NGO to initiate proceedings aimed at protecting the environment, even where the NGO itself was not a direct victim of the harm. This decision reflects an important shift towards a more liberal and purposive interpretation of locus standi in environmental litigation, signalling that environmental protection is a matter of public interest that warrants broader access to the courts.

This paper explores the evolution of locus standi in Nigeria, with a focus on how earlier judicial approaches constrained access to environmental justice. It examines the *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch* case as a landmark decision and discusses its implications for public interest litigation in environmental matters. The paper also considers the need for legislative reform to consolidate these gains and align Nigeria's environmental standing rules with international best practices, ensuring that the law serves not only private rights but also the collective interest in a safe, healthy, and sustainable environment.

2.0 The Concept of Locus Standi

The term '*locus standi*' means the legal capacity to institute proceedings in a court of law and is used interchangeably with terms like 'standing' or 'title to sue'. It has been held in numerous cases to be the right or competence to initiate proceedings in a court of law for redress or assertion of a right enforceable at law.³

Locus Standi is the starting point in litigations that affects access to justice, jurisdiction, judicial powers and remediation of wrongs in environmental matters as well as other matters including constitutional law and Administrative law. *Locus standi* focuses on the question whether an applicant or party instituting an action for

³ *Owodunni v Reg. Trustees of CCC (2000) 2 WRN 29; Ladejobi v Oguntayo (2004) 7 SC (Pt. 10 159 at 170; Sunday v INEC [2008]*

33 WRN 141 at 164

remedies or judicial review is entitled to invoke the jurisdiction of the court.⁴ It is generally considered as a threshold issue that must be decided in favour of the applicant or party before the jurisdiction of the court can be invoked.⁵

Fundamentally, *locus standi* is the way in which the courts determine who may be an applicant for judicial review or remedies.⁶ If a particular applicant is found to have a *locus standi* then they will be permitted to have their case heard or initiated. On the other hand, if the applicant is not found to have standing to bring the action, the court will not hear their grievance.⁷ The rule was developed primarily to protect the courts from being used as a playground by professional litigants, meddlesome interlopers and busy bodies that really have no real stake or interest in the subject matter of the suit.⁸

2.1 Sources of *Locus Standi*

Rules of *Locus Standi* for national courts in any jurisdiction anywhere in the world can come from one or more of four sources:

1. **Constitution:** A Constitution may provide a human right to a safe/clean/quality environment, in which case standing to protect that right is itself deemed to be a constitutional right. In countries like Kenya and Brazil, with a constitutional right to a quality environment, any person has *locus standi* to bring suit if their environmental human rights are infringed upon, including public interest groups and NGOs. The countries with constitutional human-environmental rights typically have the most open standing. India is an extreme case. India allows individuals to file human-environmental rights cases *directly in the Supreme Court* (bypassing the trial and appeals levels entirely), even for very minor or localized grievances.⁹

⁴ Oyelowo O., *Locus Standi and Administrative Law in Nigeria: Need for Clarity of Approach by the Courts*, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology* ISSN: 2313-3759 Vol. 3 No. 1; January 2016

⁵ Ibid

⁶ Ibid

⁷ Akintunde Emiola, *Remedies in Administrative Law (2000)* pp. 161-164; available at <http://www.lawteacher.net/free-law-essays/administrative-law/basic-idea-of-locus-standi.php#ixzz3u3XdyomB>. Accessed on 11th March, 2021

⁸ *Taiwo v Adegboro* [2011] 11 NWLR (Pt. 1259) 562 at 579 per Rhodes-Vivour JSC (SC)

⁹ Rajamani, Lavanya. 2007. Public Interest Environmental Litigation in India: Exploring Issues of Access, Participation, Equity, Effectiveness and Sustainability. *Journal of Environmental Law* 19:293-321. Available at <http://jel.oxfordjournals.org/cgi/content/full/19/3/293>. Accessed on 13th March, 2025.

Commenting on the India's position, Professor Lavanya Rajamani points out:

“A few activist judges in the late 1970s and early 1980s, in a series of high profile cases bristling with procedural innovations and doctrinal creativity, laid the groundwork for the growth of public interest litigation in India. The most significant of these cases is *S.P. Gupta v Union of India* in which Justice Bhagwati relaxed the rule of *locus standi*, and opened up the doors of the Supreme Court to public-spirited citizens – both those wishing to espouse the cause of the poor and oppressed (representative standing) and those wishing to enforce performance of public duties (citizen standing).”¹⁰

However, in Nigeria, the 1999 Nigerian Constitution does not provide for a fundamental right to a healthy environment. Environmental provisions in the 1999 Constitution are contained in Chapter II of the Constitution which covers the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy. Principles of State Policy constitute abstract objective constitutional provisions that are to guide the state in its decision-making processes. Section 20 of the 1999 Constitution provides that the state shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria. The Section places an obligatory duty on the State to direct its policies towards achieving the above environmental objective. However, it does not place any corresponding legal right on the citizens to enforce such provision or any other provisions of the Chapter in the event of non-compliance by the State.¹¹ The non-justiciability of the provisions of the Constitution on fundamental objectives and directive principles is a major setback of the Constitution and has led to a lot of criticism by constitutional scholars and writers.¹² It is contrary to Nigeria's posture on the international scene and her international obligations as contained in ratified treaties.¹³

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ Popoola E.O, 'Appraisal of the Contemporary Jurisprudence on the Right to Environment: A Case Study of Nigeria and South Africa'. Available at [http://www.eduproject.com.ng/law/Appraisal of the Contemporary Jurisprudence on the Right to Environment: A Case Study of Nigeria and South Africa/index](http://www.eduproject.com.ng/law/Appraisal%20of%20the%20Contemporary%20Jurisprudence%20on%20the%20Right%20to%20Environment:%20A%20Case%20Study%20of%20Nigeria%20and%20South%20Africa/index). Accessed on 12th February, 2021

¹² Alemika, E.O., (2000) Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principle of State Policy Within the Framework of a Liberal Economy. In: Ayua, I.A. et al (eds.) *Op cit.* Gye-Wado, O. (2000) Fundamental Human Rights and Corresponding Civic Obligations under the 1999 Constitution. In: Ayua et al. (eds.) *Op cit.* Joyce, E.M., and Igweike, K. (1982) *Introduction to 1979 Nigerian Constitution*. The Macmillan Press, p. 56.

¹³ Popoola E.O, *Op.cit*

2. Legislature: In adopting a law, the legislature often expressly or impliedly indicates who may file cases regarding violations of that law. Several jurisdictions have incorporated rules of *locus standi* in their statutes. South Africa's law is one such example. South Africa's environmental legislation provides:

(1) Any person or group of persons may seek appropriate relief in respect of any breach or threatened breach of any provision of the National Environmental Management Act, including a principle contained in Chapter 1, or any other statutory provision concerned with the protection of the environment or the use of natural resources –

(a) in that person's or group of person's own interest;

(b) In the interest of, or on behalf of, a person who is, for practical reasons, unable to institute such proceedings;

(c) In the interest of or on behalf of a group or class of persons whose interests are affected;

(d) In the public interest; and

(e) In the interest of protecting the environment.¹⁴

In India in 2010, the Indian Parliament enacted a legislation establishing the new "Green Tribunal" which is vested with more open standing. Recently, the Tribunal held that it can hear applications from "any person aggrieved" by government approvals of various industrial, dam, and other infrastructure projects based on Environmental Impact Assessment (EIAs).¹⁵

3. Court rules: In any jurisdiction, courts may provide standing requirements in their court operating rules.

4. Common law rule or Court rulings: some "common law" jurisdictions including Nigeria still apply the common law rules of *locus standi*. Also in common law jurisdictions such as (England, British Commonwealth countries, and others), judges may announce standing rules in their decisions as a matter of their common

¹⁴ See section 32 of the South Africa National Environmental Management Act 107 of 1998.

¹⁵ Pring, G. and Pring C. (2009). *Greening Justice: Creating and Improving Environmental Courts and Tribunals*, at 6-9 (hereafter *Greening Justice*), <http://www.law.du.edu/ect-study>. Accessed on 11th February, 2021

law powers (judge-made law based not on constitutional or legislative law, but on what is deemed reasonable or fair).¹⁶ Nigeria also falls under this category.

The doctrine of *Locus standi* as applied in Nigeria today has its root in common law as developed in England. At common law, a person who approaches a court for relief is required to have an interest in the subject matter of the litigation in the sense of being personally adversely affected by the alleged wrong. The applicant/plaintiff must allege that his or her rights have been infringed. It is not enough for the applicant/plaintiff to allege that the defendant has infringed the rights of someone else, or that the defendant is acting contrary to the law and that it is in the public interest that the court grants relief.¹⁷ Thus, under the common law, a person could only approach a court of law if he or she has sufficient, direct and personal interest in the matter. A plaintiff must in general show that he or she has some special interest or has sustained some special damage greater than that sustained by an ordinary member of the public.¹⁸

Interpreting the above common law position for environmental matters would mean that litigants seeking financial compensation from polluters who can be proved to have caused harm to their health or property could be sued. Also, litigants who are desirous of stopping nuisance that interfered with their enjoyment of their property, such as noxious odours or toxic spills would similarly be able to maintain a suit. Regrettably, many environmental injuries are less direct or personal.¹⁹ For instance, an oil spill may pollute surface water intertidal creek that is used but not owned by people in a community for fishing and recreation. In such situations, an individual may not be able to demonstrate a directly affected legal interest that would have enabled him to establish standing under the common law.²⁰

For example in *Amos & Anor v. Shell B.P. Petroleum Co of Nigeria Limited & Anor*,²¹ the plaintiffs sued the defendants in nuisance for constructing a dam across their creek

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ Elijah Adewale Taiwo, "Enforcement of fundamental rights and the standing rules under the Nigerian Constitution: A need for a more liberal provision", AHRLJ Vol.9 No. 2 (2009) 546-575.

¹⁸ Oyelowo O., *Locus Standi and Administrative Law in Nigeria: Need for Clarity of Approach by the Courts*, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology* ISSN: 2313-3759 Vol. 3 No. 1; January 2016

¹⁹ Olanreesju F & Ojo G. 'Resource Governance and Access to Justice: Innovating Best Practices in Aid of Nigeria's Oil Pollution Victims' NIALS Journal of Environmental Law

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ (1974) 3 ESCLR 486

as a result of which their farms were flooded and damaged. The position of the court, among others, was that since the creek was a public waterway, blocking it constituted a public nuisance and there had to be proof that the plaintiffs had suffered damage peculiar to them. Again, in *Allar Iron v. Shell B.P.*,²² the High Court refused a prayer for injunction to restrain the defendant from further polluting lands, creeks and fish ponds on grounds that the injunction if granted could stop the defendant's trade and render many unemployed and even affect the country's revenue since oil was the main income generator. According to the court, the balance of convenience was clearly not on the side of the plaintiffs.

Commenting on the decision of the court in *Allar Iron* above, Olanrewaju F, argued that the Court obviously lacked an understanding of environmental issues and key principles of sustainable development. He contended that the purpose of the injunctive relief being sought in the case was to prevent the respondent from continuing to cause environmental damage until determination of the suit. This is in order to avoid where a case is won but the damage is already and irrevocably done.²³

In *Oronto Douglas v. Shell Petroleum Development Company Ltd & 5 Ors*,²⁴ the plaintiff sought a declaration to get the defendant to comply with the provision of the Environmental Impact Assessment Act in relation to liquefied natural gas projects at Bonny. The trial court held that the plaintiff had no standing to institute the action since he had shown no *prima facie* evidence that his rights was affected or any direct injury was caused to him or that he suffered any injury more than the generality of the people. On appeal, the court of Appeal accepted the case for trial on the ground that it was erroneous to conclude that the appellant had no standing without looking at the statement of claim or in the absence of any evidence. However, the plaintiff eventually lost the case and the LNG project continued.

One wonders why Nigeria sticks to the old Common rule on *locus standi* rigidly. Even England that Nigeria seems to copy its common law rule now favours open standing. England generally requires only that the plaintiff have "a sufficient interest," which is construed liberally, to allow effective access to justice. Accordingly, it was held:

²² Suit No. WW189/7

²³ Olanreesju F & Ojo G. Op.cit

²⁴ (1991) 2 NWLR (Pt.591. 466

“...it would... be a grave gap in our system of public law if a pressure group... or even a single public spirited taxpayer, were prevented by outdated technical rules of *locus standi* from bringing the matter to the attention of the court to vindicate the rule of law and get the unlawful conduct stopped”²⁵

3.0 Concept of Sufficient Interest

Generally, the test for resolving the issue of *locus standi* in environmental law as well as other laws, especially in the area of administrative law, has been held in a plethora of Nigerian cases to depend on whether the claimant has sufficient legal interest to institute the action, and not whether the action was bound to fail in any event.²⁶ In *Chijuka v Maduewesi*²⁷ responding to the question on what determines *locus standi* to file an action, the Court of Appeal stated per Muhktar JCA that:

A plaintiff must show sufficient interest in the suit or matter in order to have *locus standi* to sue. One criterion of sufficient interest is whether the party could be joined as a party in the suit. Another criterion is whether the party seeking the redress or remedy will suffer some injury or hardship arising from the litigation. If the judge is satisfied that he will so suffer, then he must be heard as he is entitled to be heard.

The Supreme Court has also in several cases, adopted this line of reasoning.²⁸ For example, in *Adetona v Zenith Int'l Bank Plc*,²⁹ it was held that for a person to have *locus standi*, he must show that his civil rights and obligations have been or are in danger of being infringed and that he has sufficient legal interest in seeking redress in a court of law. The Supreme Court then gave the meaning of “interest” in relation to *locus standi* thus:

A person has an interest in a thing when he has rights, advantages, duties, liabilities, losses or the like connected with the thing, whether present or future, ascertained or potential provided that the connection, and in the case of potential rights and duties,

²⁵ Cited in Pring, G. and Pring C. Op.cit

²⁶ Olanrewaju Opcit

²⁷ [2011] 16 NWLR (Pt.1272) 181 at 205 per Muhktar JCA

²⁸ *Uwazuruonye v Gov., Imo State* [2013] 8 NWLR (Pt. 1355) 28 at 51-52 per Onnenghen JSC; *Pam v Mohammed*(2008) 16 NWLR (Pt. 1112) 1

²⁹ [2011] NWLR (Pt. 1279) 627 at 654-655 per Muhammed JSC, relying on *Adesanya V President* (1981) 2 NCLR 358; *Lawal v Salami* 92002) 2 NWLR (Pt. 752) 687; *odeleye v Adepegba* (2001) 5 NWLR (Pt. 706) 330. See also *ASUU v BPE*[2013] 14 NWLR (Pt. 1374) 398 at 415.

the possibility, is not too remote.³⁰ Nigeria has therefore like most Commonwealth systems³¹ adopted the test of 'sufficient interest' in interpreting *locus standi*, particularly in environmental law cases. Thus, an applicant/plaintiff must plead sufficient interest to sustain and meet *locus standi* requirement. Therefore, even where the applicants brought representative actions as in the case of NGO instituting an action on behalf of victims, it will not succeed if they fail to establish sufficient interest to meet the requisite *locus standi* to sustain the action.

It is apparent that there is no clearly established right of standing beyond that recognized under the common law. The restrictive interpretation was first given in the famous 1981 Supreme Court case of *Adesanya v. President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria*³² while interpreting section 6(6)(b) of Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1979.³³ In that case, the Supreme Court noted that it is only the Attorney-General that asserts public right and since it was not the Attorney-General that brought the case the court refused standing.³⁴ There was denial of standing for individuals³⁵ from that time until the famous case of *Akilu v. Fawehinmi*³⁶ where the Supreme Court broadened the scope of standing in Nigeria. Again, the Supreme Court in the 1991 case of *Adeniran and Anor v. Interland Transport Limited*³⁷ specifically reversed its own decision to widen the rule of *locus standi*.

Despite the *Adeniran and Akilus' cases*, there has been conflicting decisions on standing in environmental matters, some successive court pronouncements being restrictive³⁸ and others being liberal.³⁹ However, the 2009 Fundamental Rights

³⁰ Ibid at 648 per Chukwuma-Eneh, referring to *Imade v Mil. Admin., Edo State (2001)* 6 NWLR (Pt. 709) 478

³¹ For a full discussion of English law on *locus standi*, see Paul Craig, *Administrative Law*, 7th edition, (2012, Sweet & Maxwell Thomson Reuters) 770 - 786

³² [1981] 2 NCLR 358.

³³ Now 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

³⁴ However, Fatayi Williams JSC gave a dissenting judgment allowing standing in the case.

³⁵ *Oloriode v. Oyebi* (1984) 5 SC 1; *Thomas v. Olufosoye* (1986) 1 NWLR (pt. 18) 669; *AG Kaduna State v. Hassan* (1985) 2 NWLR (pt. 8) 483; *Orogan v. Soremekun* (1986) 5 NWLR (pt. 44) 688; *Egbe v. Adefarasin* (1987) 1 NWLR (pt. 47) 1; and *Bolaji v. Bamgbose* (1986) 4 NWLR (pt. 37) 632.

³⁶ (No.2) (1989) 2 NWLR (pt 102) 122

³⁷ (1991) 9 NWLR (pt 214) 155

³⁸ *Gbemre v. SPDC and Ors* (2005) Suit No. FHC/B/CS/53/05; *SPDC v. Chief Otoko and others* (1990) 6 NWLR (pt. 159) 693; *N.N.P.C. v. SELE* (2004) All FWLR (pt. 223) 1859 CA and *Oronto Douglas v. SPDC* Suit No. FHC/25C/573/93, unreported, delivered on 17 February 1997.

³⁹ See *Adeniran and Anor v. Interland Transport Limited* (1991) 9 NWLR, (pt 214) 155; *SPDC v. Nwauka* (2001) 10 NWLR (pt. 720) 64; *SPDC v. Elder Banigo I. Firibeb & anor* (2011) LPELR-9783(CA).

(Enforcement Procedure) Rules of 2009 made a departure from the 1979 Rules under which *Adesanya's case* was decided by recognising the liberal standing.⁴⁰ Preamble 3(e) provides that no human rights case may be dismissed or struck out for want of standing to sue.⁴¹ Preamble 3(d) requires a Nigerian court to pursue enhanced access to justice for all classes of litigants, especially the poor, the illiterate, the uninformed, the vulnerable, the incarcerated and the unrepresented. The federal High Court Rules is limited to issues concerning enforcement of fundamental Human rights generally; it does extend to environmental claims and other environmental related issues.

In environmental cases, the disagreement and inconsistency in judicial decisions regarding standing continued mostly being restrictive.⁴² As a result, several environmental litigations in Nigeria have failed because of a lack of *locus standi*. Because of these frustrations and in order to find a way around the issue of *locus standi* in environmental related matters, NGOs have resorted to jurisdictions outside Nigeria to seek environmental justice for victims of environmental degradation.⁴³ The case of Registered Trustees of the Socio-Economic Rights & Accountability Project (SERAP) v. President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria & Ors⁴⁴ is one example of several other cases. In that case an NGO filed a case at the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) court of Justice. The matter was filed on behalf of victims of environmental pollution at the Niger Delta seeking environmental justice. Happily, the Supreme Court has recently in 2019 to be precised liberalized the position of the law on locus standi in environmental matters in Public Interest Litigations.

4.0 Supreme Court Decision on Locus Standi in Environmental Matters

In 2019, the Supreme Court of Nigeria in the case of *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. N.N.P.C*⁴⁵ liberalized the principle of *locus standi* in environmental litigations. The

⁴⁰ Okwonkwo E.C. Op cit

⁴¹ Available at <<http://accesstojustice-ng.org/2009%20FREP%20RULES.pdf>> accessed 12 June 2020. Also, its Order 111, Rule 1 provides that an application for fundamental right enforcement shall not be affected by any limitation statute.

⁴² Okwonkwo E.C. Op cit See also *SPDC v. Chief Otoko and Others* (1990) 6 NWLR (pt. 159) 693; *N.N.P.C. v. SELE* (2004) ALL FWLR (pt. 223) 1859 CA, but see *SPDC v. Elder Banigo I. Firibeb & anor* (2011) LPELR- 9783(CA, 1380.

⁴³ S.A. Fagbemi & A. R. Akpanke Environmental Litigation in Nigeria: The Role Of The Judiciary, NAUJILJ 10 (2) 2019, For example see the case of *Registered Trustees of the Socio-Economic Rights & Accountability Project (SERAP) v. President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria & Ors* (*supra*)

⁴⁴ ECW/CCJ/JUD/18/12

⁴⁵ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt.1666) 518 SC or [2019] 5 NWLR (Pt. 1666) 518

dispute arose from an oil spill in Abia State, when a corroded pipeline operated by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) ruptured and discharged crude oil into the Ineh and Aku streams and rivers. The spill allegedly caused significant environmental damage, contaminating water bodies and disrupting the livelihoods of nearby communities. The Centre for Oil Pollution Watch (the Centre), a registered Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) committed to the reinstatement, restoration, and remediation of environments impaired by oil spills, wrote to NNPC demanding that it clean up and rehabilitate the affected areas. When NNPC failed to take remedial action, the Centre instituted proceedings at the Federal High Court in Lagos, seeking orders compelling NNPC to clean up and restore the polluted environment.

At the trial, NNPC denied responsibility for the oil spill and, in a preliminary objection, challenged the locus standi of the Centre to institute the suit. It argued that the NGO was not directly affected by the oil spill and therefore lacked the legal standing to sue. The Federal High Court upheld this objection, holding that the Centre had not shown sufficient personal interest or injury to warrant bringing the action. The court struck out the suit, applying the traditional, restrictive interpretation of locus standi under Nigerian law.

Dissatisfied with the ruling, the Centre appealed to the Court of Appeal. However, the appellate court affirmed the decision of the Federal High Court. It agreed that the Centre had not demonstrated that its civil rights or obligations were in danger of infringement and therefore lacked the standing to sue. The Court of Appeal maintained that only a person or entity directly affected by an environmental harm could seek redress, thereby excluding public interest claims by NGOs. Still aggrieved, the Centre appealed to the Supreme Court. The then Chief Justice of Nigeria, Walter Onnoghen CJN, empanelled a full court to hear the appeal. The sole issue for determination was whether the Court of Appeal was right in dismissing the appellant's case for want of locus standi.

The Supreme Court received arguments from counsel for the parties and also invited the Honourable Attorney-General of the Federation (represented by Dayo Apata, Solicitor-General of the Federation) and four Senior Advocates of Nigeria Wole Olanipekun, Adegboyega Awomolo, Abubakar Mahmud, and Lucius Nwosu as amici curiae ("friends of the court") to offer their perspectives on the question before the court.

In a landmark judgment delivered in 2019, the Supreme Court allowed the appeal and held that an NGO has the requisite *locus standi* to sue in environmental matters. The Court observed that other common law jurisdictions, such as the United Kingdom, India, Canada, and Australia, had long abandoned a narrow and rigid application of *locus standi*, especially in public interest litigation. It reasoned that the term “person” under the Interpretation Act includes “anybody” or “persons corporate” or “incorporated.”

The Court found that paragraphs 1 and 2 of the amended statement of claim sufficiently disclosed the appellant’s interest in the matter and therefore conferred standing. It emphasised that the NNPC, being a public authority, had statutory and constitutional obligations to protect the environment, and that its failure to do so had occasioned public injury.

Justice Nweze, JSC, delivering the leading judgment, stated:

“It is by liberalising the rule of *locus standi* that it is possible to effectively police the corridors of power and prevent violations of law... in environmental matters, such as the instant one, NGOs, such as the plaintiff in this case, have the requisite *standi* to sue.”

In his concurring opinion, Onnoghen CJN remarked:

“The plaintiff cannot, in any way, be described as a busy body or interloper. This is public interest litigation... the law on *locus standi*... now encompasses public-spirited individuals and NGOs.”

This judgment marked a departure from the previously restrictive Nigerian approach to standing in environmental cases, allowing NGOs to bring actions on behalf of affected communities. However, it remains unclear whether the decision completely discarded the “sufficient interest” test, as the Court still assessed the NGO’s connection to the case before granting standing.

5.0 Call for Further Reform: Aftermath of the Supreme Court Decision

Certainly, the innovative decision of the Supreme Court is highly commendable and has further renewed public confidence in the judiciary as the last hope of the common man and proves the capacity of our courts system in judicial activism. However, the paper calls for further reform and extension of the scope of *locus standi* through environmental legislation as done in many jurisdictions, particularly ones that have

established environmental courts. Such legislation could avoid likely conflicting decisions in future that could cause confusion as had happened in the past. Particularly considering the fact that the decision of the Supreme Court is not very clear on whether the concept of ‘sufficient interest’ is completely thrown away in our environmental jurisprudence. The paper also strongly advocates that the reform in legislation should include alternative method of dispute resolution to effectively enforce the legislation on *locus standi*. Thus the paper proposes establishment of environmental court in Nigeria. The court would bypass the problem of locus standi and myriads of other problems inherent in our courts system hampering access to environmental justice in Nigeria. The reform in the legislation should bring our laws on *locus standi* in line with the best practices.

For example, in Philippines, any person or group of persons, by themselves or through duly-authorized representatives, or in representation of others, including generations yet unborn, in a class suit, may file a civil action involving a violation or enforcement of environmental laws.⁴⁶ Persons that may institute actions in Philippines shall include:

- (a) Any citizen;
- (b) Minors with the assistance of their parents or guardians;
- (c) People’s and non-governmental organizations and public interest groups;
- (d) Indigenous peoples and local communities;
- (e) Others similarly situated.⁴⁷ Parties in interest shall have the right to intervene to protect their own individual interest.⁴⁸

Similarly, the New South Wales’ environmental law states that “Any person” may sue to restrain a violation of the law.⁴⁹ In Trinidad and Tobago, any individual or group of individuals expressing a general interest in the environment or specific concerns can bring a direct party action alleging a violation of the Environmental Management

⁴⁶ Supreme Court of Philippines Environmental Rules

⁴⁷ Ibid

⁴⁸ Ibid

⁴⁹ McAllister, Lesley K. Litigating climate change at the coal mine. In *Adjudicating climate change: State, national, and international approaches*, eds William C. G. Burns and Hari M. Osofsky, 48-71. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Act.⁵⁰ Environmental law in Sudan provides that any person can lodge a claim where there has been environmental damage, with no proof of direct connection to such damage.⁵¹ UNEP recommends the open approach in no uncertain terms: “States should provide broad and inclusive interpretation of standing in proceedings concerned with environmental matters”⁵²

Surprisingly, the recent Supreme Court decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v NNPC*⁵³ has generated some concerns among some legal scholars. For example Olatunbosun A. I. and Onu K.O.N⁵⁴ recently expressed the worry that such liberalised approach to *locus standi* in environmental litigation adopted by the Supreme Court may open the floodgates of the court to unnecessary litigation, vexatious litigants, and busy body NGOs. And those unnecessary litigations may distract IOCs and affect their productivity; hence, spelling a downturn on Nigeria's economy that is oil-centric.⁵⁵ With due respect to the learned writers such worry is not plausible and would easily be discarded looking at the experience of countries that have the most open standing rules for years, notably, jurisdictions that have established environmental courts.

Several studies fail to support the negative assumptions that are advanced to support restrictive standing. For example, the Australian Law Reform Commission reviewed the arguments against more open standing and found them to be rebuttable. In Australia, the arguments are similar to those expressed by some Nigerian writers against open standing. The four primary reasons given for restricting access in Australia are that relaxed rules will cause (1) a “flood” of litigation, (2) “frivolous or vexatious” lawsuits, (3) courts exceeding their role, and (4) delay and increased cost for property and economic development.⁵⁶ The Commission in 1985 and again in 1996

⁵⁰ Pring and Ping Op.cit

⁵¹ Ibid

⁵² Ibid

⁵³ [2019] 5 NWLR (part 1666) 518.

⁵⁴ Olatunbosun A. I. and Onu K.O.N., The Liberalisation of *Locus Standi* in Environmental Cases in Nigeria: An Appraisal of The Supreme Court's Decision in *Centre For Oil Pollution Watch V NNPC*, The Gravitas Review of Business & Property Law *June 2020 Vol.11 No.2*

⁵⁵ Ibid

⁵⁶ Pring, G. and Pring C. Op.cit

found that the first three are easily dealt with and the fourth is legitimate but must be balanced against the pro-standing counterarguments.⁵⁷

Regarding the first “flood” argument:

The standing rules do not work as a gate, guarding against a flood of litigation or guarding against damaging and meddlesome interference. Even if there were flood, standing tests are not an effective restraint. Where there is a need for protection against damaging interference in government regulation of business and other activities, this requires better case management and better government decision making.⁵⁸

Regarding the second or “frivolous-vexatious” argument, the Australian Commission amusingly observes that a court can have “an ‘open door’, but with a ‘pest screen’”:

“These claims are unfounded. Liberalisation of standing in certain areas – even to the extent of *allowing any person to sue* – has not produced a rash of litigation. The Courts... possess a number of powers which can be used to prevent frivolous claims being made: for example, the power to strike out a vexatious claim and the power to declare individual litigants vexatious. Similarly, there is no evidence that the phenomenon of a large number of plaintiffs, all suing on the same course of action, will arise frequently if standing is widened.”⁵⁹

Regarding the third or improper-role argument, the Commission concludes:

“Restrictive standing rules are sometimes said to be necessary because public interest litigation is likely to impose on courts challenges for which they are inadequately equipped [and which are more properly the role of the legislative and executive branches]. But there is no evidence that the courts are unfitted to determine the legal questions that arise in reviewing the actions of administrative officers and dealing with other forms of public interest litigation. In any event, if this were the case, the proper

⁵⁷ Ibid

⁵⁸ Australian Law Reform Commission. 1985. *Standing in Public Interest Litigation* (ALRC Report No. 27). Canberra: Australian Government Publishing Service. Available at <http://www.austlii.edu.au/au/other/alrc/publications/reports/27/>. See also 1995. *Beyond the Doorkeeper – Standing to Sue for Public Remedies* (ALRC Report No. 78). Canberra: Australian Government Publishing Service. Available from <http://www.austlii.edu.au/au/other/alrc/publications/reports/78/ALRC78.html>.

⁵⁹ Ibid see also Pring, G. and Pring C. (2009). *Greening Justice: Creating and Improving Environmental Courts*

and Tribunals, opcit

response would be to limit expressly [in legislation] the types of case in which the courts could intervene, rather than use the law of standing to deny to some plaintiffs (though not others) the right to approach the courts.”⁶⁰

Regarding the fourth argument – effect of litigation on economic development – the Commission finds it a legitimate issue, but needing to be balanced against the benefits of Public Interest Litigations.⁶¹ “Lawsuits can and do add to the time, cost, and feasibility of development, from a neighbor’s new fence to a multi-billion-dollar oil and gas refinery. Pro-development governments, especially in impoverished nations, make it clear that they do not want development or foreign direct investment delayed, discouraged, or otherwise impeded by litigation and are less concerned about environmental and community protection than economic advancement. However, sustainable development requires that economic concerns must be balanced against the environmental, social, cultural, human rights, and other serious legal and social concerns. Jurisdictions have found that suppressing the filing of legitimate grievances can be counterproductive, leading to societal unrest, and that access to justice is a good safety valve.”⁶²

The Australian Law Reform Commission concluded that the restrictive law on standing for Public Interest Litigation is counterproductive. It acts as an extra source of unnecessary legal costs and delay. It does not act as an effective filter for disputes that are futile, vexatious or otherwise inappropriate for litigation. Such a filter is provided by other laws and discretions available to the court.⁶³ Restrictive standing would also act as an unpredictable technical barrier. In particular, ‘sufficient interest’ test can be uncertain, complicated, inconsistent and overly dependent on subjective value judgments.⁶⁴ This can make the legal system appear unfair, inefficient and ineffective.⁶⁵ According to the Commission, the current law (restrictive) standing is therefore a doorkeeper that courts do not need as protection and litigants cannot

⁶⁰ Ibid

⁶¹ Ibid

⁶² Pring, G. & S. Noé. 2002. The Emerging International Law of Public Participation Affecting Global Mining, Energy, and Resources Development. Chapter 1 in *Human Rights in Natural Resources Development: Public Participation in the Sustainable Development of Mining and Energy Resources*, edited by D. Zillman, et al. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

⁶³ Pring, G. and Pring C. (2009), Op.cit

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ Ibid

afford.⁶⁶ The findings of the Australian Law Commission led to the reform on rules of standing in Australia moving away from the hitherto restrictive approach to a more liberalize rules on *locus standi*.

One cannot agree more with the finding of the Australian Law Reform Commission which is similarly applicable to Nigerian situation and thus some of the concerns raised against more open standing will not hold water. Though we are aware that the Attorney General is legally considered to be the defender of public interest and the Nigerian Constitution made provision for an Attorney General who is the Chief Law Officer and a Minister of Justice of the Federation and empowers him to commence or enter *nolle prosequere* in the public interest.⁶⁷ However, it is doubtful whether the Attorney-General can truly represent the public interest giving the fact that he is a member of the government, especially where the public interest conflicts with government's interest.⁶⁸ On this issue Aboki JSC observed in *Fawehinmi v President*⁶⁹ thus:

'In our present reality, the Attorney General of the Federation is also the Minister of Justice and a member of the Executive cabinet. He may not be disposed to instituting an action against the Government in which he is part of, it may tantamount to the Federal Government suing itself. Definitely he will not perform such duty... He further inquired 'who will approach the Court to challenge the Government where it violates or fails to enforce any provisions of the Constitution or the laws where the Attorney-General will not.'

There are convincing reasons to liberalize locus standi in public interest litigation particularly in environmental cases. A group of citizens or environmental NGOs have a crucial role to play as monitors of environmental activities, public educators,

⁶⁶ Australian Law Reform Commission 1996, available at <https://www.alrc.gov.au/inquiry/standing-in-public-interest-litigation>, accessed on 20/09/2024

⁶⁷ The office of Attorney General and Commissioner for Justice is also created for each state of the federation. Section 174(3) provides, 'in exercising his powers, the Attorney-General of the Federation shall have regard to the public interest, the interest of justice and the need to prevent abuse of legal process.'

⁶⁸ Oyelowo O., *opcit*

⁶⁹ (2008) 23 WRN 65.

motivators, and defenders of the environment and are highly organized to mount environmental litigation.⁷⁰

6.0 Conclusion

The decision of the apex court has rekindled public confidence in the Nigerian judiciary as the true last hope of the common man. In this judgment, the Supreme Court demonstrated commendable judicial activism, notwithstanding that the defendant was the highest revenue-generating agency of the Federal Government. Undoubtedly, the Court has delivered a landmark ruling that liberalizes the principle of locus standi in Nigeria.

To further consolidate this progressive development and strengthen access to justice in environmental matters, this study strongly recommends that the National Assembly enact legislation adopting the most open standing provisions in line with international best practices. Such legislation should also establish a specialized Environmental Court in Nigeria, as exists in many jurisdictions, including Australia, the United States, Sweden, and the Philippines.

A dedicated Environmental Court, vested with exclusive jurisdiction over environmental and sustainable development matters, would not only innovatively apply liberal locus standi rules but also address the systemic challenges currently hindering effective access to justice. By removing procedural bottlenecks and ensuring the speedy, expert resolution of environmental disputes, such a court would significantly enhance environmental governance and safeguard the rights of present and future generations.

⁷⁰ MMadu R.A., *Judicial Attitude to Environmental Litigation and Access to Environmental Justice in Nigeria: Lessons From Kiobel*, AFe Babalola University Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy, Vol. 2 Iss.1 (2013), pp 149-170